

IMPROVING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE INSTRUCTION IN MEDICAL STUDIES THROUGH DIGITALIZATION

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Abstract. *The present paper focuses on the benefits of technology-based learning and assessment units for clinical communicative competence in medical studies, using the voLeA project as an example.*

Keywords: *medical conversation, competence measurement, e-learning, digitalization, video reflection, Situational Judgement Test.*

The teaching of communicative competence plays an increasingly important role in medical education. In addition to traditional teaching formats, such as role-plays with simulated patients, technology-based approaches become more important in medical education. Teaching materials are increasingly augmented by videos of simulated doctor-patient conversations. This combination allows the content of teaching materials to be demonstrated with video or for videos to create a basis for reflection activities. In addition, conversation videos can illustrate different qualities of clinical communication and serve as illustrative material for describing particular issues in more detail. In addition to teaching clinical communicative competence, the assessment of this competence also plays an important role in medical educational research. So far, this has mainly been conducted through direct observation using checklists or rating scales. Relatively little is known about the assessment of communicative competence using standardized online-based tests. Situational Judgement Tests (SJTs) offer a promising approach in this respect. The BMBF-funded (BMBF = Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung – Federal Ministry of Education and Research) joint project *voLeA (Entwicklung videobasierter Lehr- und Assessmentmodule zur Gesprächskompetenz im Medizinstudium = Development of video-based teaching and assessment modules for communicative competence in medical studies)* addresses these two issues. Specifically, the project is engaged in developing e-learning modules to promote communicative competence and an assessment of this competence using an SJT.

Holding conversations with patients is one of the most common aspects of clinical practice. Numerous studies have shown that the quality of communication between doctors and patients has an influence on patients' recovery as well as on the relationship with their doctors. Professionally conducted clinical communication also has a positive effect on doctors' health, lowering stress levels and so reducing the risk of burnout. In view of these research findings, it can be assumed that the investment in improving the communicative competence of doctors will have a direct influence on the quality of medical care [5].

The topic of professional clinical communication is now an integral part of the education of doctors in most human medicine curricula, but often falls short in terms of reach and scope. For this reason, the German government has introduced a directive on the reform of medical studies in its 2020 Master Plan, in which it focuses on strengthening the teaching of communication with patients for (prospective) doctors [6]. The national longitudinal model curriculum Communication

in Medicine [7], which comprises 350 compulsory core units and 100 elective units, serves as the framework for implementing this directive. The implementation of these extensive requirements presents most medical faculties with immense time, staffing and financial challenges. It therefore makes little sense to reinforce the communication skills of young doctors solely by expanding existing curricula. Effective teaching formats for the promotion of communicative competence offer a promising alternative since they are suitable for large groups of students and are therefore also advantageous from a resource perspective.

Developments in the area of digitalization are opening up new opportunities for devising innovative teaching approaches and making education in communicative competence for prospective doctors both more instructionally versatile and more effective. In recent years, various empirical studies have investigated and demonstrated the potential of video-based e-learning for the promotion of clinical communicative competencies [7].

The *voLeA* (Development of video-based teaching and assessment modules for communicative competence in medical studies) joint project, which has been funded by the BMBF since 11/2018, is therefore pursuing the goal of developing digital, video-based teaching modules for the promotion of clinical communicative competence and empirically investigating their effectiveness and implementation. Within the framework of the current, first project phase, these teaching modules will be implemented in the attendance-based curriculum for clinical communicative competence at the Faculty of Medicine at the TU Munich. At the same time, a video-based Situational Judgement Test (SJT) for the assessment of clinical communicative competence will be developed in order to assess the development of communicative competence among medical students in a valid and reliable way. This paper aims to show the potential that digitalization offers for expanding and embedding communicative competence in medical studies. To this end, we summarize the current state of research on this topic and present the *voLeA* project as an example of a concrete initiative in this area.

Competence in professional communication with patients is often referred to as communication skills in the context of medical educational research. This refers to the actual routines that (prospective) doctors should have at their disposal to ensure quality communication with patients. These include using open questions to understand a patient's concerns or communicating relevant medical information in a clear and comprehensible way [1]. In order to build on this approach and conceptualize communication as a competence, Blömeke et al.'s definition (2015) is used in our study [3]. They define communicative competence as a bundle of different, intrapersonal resources on the basis of which communicative situations in a professional context can be successfully navigated. These resources include professional knowledge (e.g., about theoretical models of interpersonal communication), attitudes (regarding the importance of professional communication) and concrete abilities and skills (in the sense of the communication skills described above) [4]. On the basis of this definition, we can reasonably assume that an instructionally versatile course program would be useful in promoting the various aspects of communicative competence. As a recent review has shown, the use of digital learning programs is particularly promising in this respect. Basically, three different forms of such programs can be distinguished:

A first group comprises video-based, interactive learning programs that use elements such as screencasts, fictional video cases and interactive exercises [2]. These learning programs often include text-based teaching of basic communicative competence, enriched by interactive tasks or

video examples. The videos also serve to illustrate successful or even faulty communication strategies and are often combined with reflective instructional items. A well-known example of this category is the doc.com platform, which is now also available in German. It comprises video-based online modules on various aspects of clinical conversations, such as delivering bad news [1].

Secondly, there are various programs that rely on computer-supported interaction between medical students and simulated patients (e.g., via Skype or video chat) as an instructional tool. Such programs involve real people assuming the role of patients and interacting with learners in real time. One such program is EQClinic, which has been shown to have a positive effect on students' ability to reflect [3].

Thirdly, the literature discusses programs in which students interact with virtual patients, whom they encounter in immersive virtual reality environments such as Second Life or MPathic. These programs therefore simulate doctor-patient conversations on a virtual level. Existing studies show a high level of acceptance of such approaches among test participants [6].

The same review reports that the computer-based programs for the training of communicative competence described above have been evaluated positively and have generally achieved high acceptance ratings. In addition, all 17 studies included in the review demonstrated effects in the development of self-efficacy expectations in the communicative field as well as learning effects in the area of knowledge about communication and communicative competence. According to M. Stewart [3], one challenge for such programs that is evident across various studies is that virtual patients are often evaluated as unrealistic. In addition, the programs in the studies cited, without exception, represent complex Treatment Packages, which involve the interplay of different instructional elements. Consequently, most of the existing studies do not permit differentiated statements about which design elements and principles determine the effectiveness of the respective programs and how these are related to specific learner characteristics. Studies therefore make the general point that it is in principle possible to promote communicative skills with the help of e-learning. However, we need to identify and distinguish the factors influencing effectiveness more precisely. Further research in this direction is urgently needed. In the next section, the *voLeA* project will be presented, followed by a discussion of the basic instructional assumptions behind the approach pursued here.

All in all, the teaching and assessment modules developed in *voLeA* – either separately or in combination – can help efficiently meet the demand for more intensive training of the communicative competence of prospective doctors.

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